

Operations Assistants for the Manned Space Program¹

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Abstract—The manned space program is facing many challenges due to the nature of current and future programs. Automation in the form of Operations Assistants is being pursued as a solution to some of these challenges. This paper describes the nature of the challenges and NASA / Johnson Space Center's approach to meeting these challenges. This includes a description of the initial phase of the Operations Assistant project and the presentation of a staged approach to incorporating intelligent agents.

facing the challenges of sustaining and developing new operations capabilities to support the growth in existing programs and to enable the advent of human exploration missions.

Mission operations are becoming increasingly distributed due to the growth in international participation and the expanded involvement of the scientific, academic, and industrial communities. Flight controllers are challenged by new roles and complex operational scenarios such as extended duration operations, long distances, and multi-vehicle control. In addition, MOD is continuously seeking to improve its processes to accomplish missions at higher levels of safety, mission success, and effectiveness.

Automation is being considered as an enabling technology to meet the aforementioned challenges. The synergistic combination of flight controllers and intelligent software, providing the function of Operations Assistants, is being pursued as the key implementation of this technology in the Mission Control Center (MCC) (figure 1).

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1. INTRODUCTION

The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), in conjunction with many international partners, is currently undertaking the development of the International Space Station (ISS). NASA is also looking ahead to future manned missions beyond low earth orbit. Meanwhile, the Space Shuttle remains a key vehicle for both the ISS missions and other scientific missions.

The Mission Operations Directorate (MOD) at Johnson Space Center (JSC) is responsible for the planning and conduct of human space flight missions. MOD is now

Figure 1 – Mission Control Center (MCC)

Operations Assistants will function as members of the flight control team and assist flight controllers in maintaining

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mission cognizance and performing duties such as data analysis, failure identification, off-nominal situation response, planning, and system/process management. By developing Operations Assistants for current missions, NASA will ensure that the technology is matured for future programs.

The initial phase of the operations assistant project consists of an electronic logging application that utilizes a data base and automates the handover report generation process. This lays the foundation for extensive future capabilities such as the use of advanced data base features (intelligent searches, tracking of open issues, reference material links) and links to information resources that will be utilized to provide an "intelligent briefing assistant" capability. In addition, the stage is set for connections to vehicle data, existing MCC software tools, and intelligent agents, which are essential for many of the Operations Assistant functions.

The work on the initial phase of the Operations Assistant has been accomplished by a team from NASA/Johnson Space Center, NASA/Ames Research Center, and Ohio State University. It will take the continued collaboration of multiple NASA centers and academia as well as the participation of other interested organizations to solve the many unique technical challenges associated with implementing intelligent agents in manned space operations. These challenges include the necessity of ensuring a high level of system safety and software reliability. Additionally, the software must be easy to develop and maintain and must function as member of the flight control team. Intelligent agent-based systems will play a key role in solving these complex problems as NASA prepares for future manned exploration missions.

2. OPERATIONAL CHALLENGES FACING THE MANNED SPACE PROGRAM

MOD is now facing the challenges of sustaining and developing new operations capabilities to support the growth in existing programs and to enable the advent of human exploration missions. The term "operations" includes all aspects of planning and executing a manned space mission. It also takes into consideration the training and planning that occur prior to the beginning of the mission. The term "operations concepts" means the manner in which these operations are carried out.

These operational challenges may be grouped into four categories.

1. Distributed Operations
2. Multi-mission / Multi-program
3. Long duration / Long distance
4. Operations Enhancements

Distributed Operations

Mission operations are becoming increasingly distributed due to the growth in international participation and the

expanded involvement of the scientific, academic, and industrial communities in research activities performed onboard and over extended periods of time. In addition to this geographic distribution, the added dimension of space-based as well as ground-based operations increases the complexity of missions.

Multi-mission / Multi-program

NASA is currently concurrently flying multiple vehicles for shuttle (figure 2) and space station (figure 3) missions. With the advent of exploration missions (figure 4), the number of concurrent missions will increase.

Figure 2- Space Shuttle

Figure 3 -Artist's Concept of Completed International Space Station (ISS)

Figure 4 - Artist's Concept of an Exploration Mission

Long Duration / Long Distance

The length of the missions MOD supports is increasing from weeks for the shuttle to several months with the space station. This will become years for future exploration

missions. Also, as long distances are encountered in exploration missions, operations support will require a shift in real-time control from the ground to onboard the spacecraft due to the inherent communications delays. Long distance and extended duration missions will also require novel ways of performing crew activity planning and crew training. Overall emphasis for these missions will be placed on providing the onboard crew with a high level of self-sufficiency while the ground will maintain overall mission cognizance and perform long term mission planning and analysis.

Operations Enhancements

In addition to responding to these challenges, MOD is continuously seeking to improve its processes to accomplish its missions at higher levels of safety, mission success and cost effectiveness.

3. OPERATIONS CONCEPTS AND TECHNOLOGY NEEDS

As the operations environment becomes more complex and busier, due the expansion of current programs and the advent of the exploration programs, it is necessary to develop and incorporate new operations concepts.

The Human Exploration Operations Team, chaired by JSC MOD personnel, has the charter to develop mission operations concepts related to all flight phases for manned missions beyond low earth orbit. These operations concepts provide the framework within which advanced technologies are pursued. This team also operates the Exploration Planning and Operations Center (ExPOC), which is used to conduct operations at exploration analog sites in order to flesh out the advanced operations concepts.

These operations concepts will require the implementation of advanced technologies in many areas, as shown in Table 1. Some of these technologies exist today but have not yet been applied to the area of manned space operations. Other technologies have not yet reached a point of maturity where they can be applied to human operations.

Details regarding these technology needs areas are included in the Advanced Operations Technology Program Plan [1].

Table 1. Technology Needs

BROAD AREA	TECHNOLOGY
Advanced Computation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agent based systems 2. Auto code generation, validation, and verification 3. Knowledge management 4. Simulation and Modeling
Intelligent Systems	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Automated Reasoning 2. Data Understanding
Mission Data Handling	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Networking and communication systems 2. Data Compression 3. Data archival / warehouse 4. Security
Human Interfaces	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Human Computer Interfaces (HCI) 2. Human Centered Computing (HCC) 3. Telepresence 4. Immersion 5. Virtual Reality 6. Natural language (including speech synthesis and voice recognition)
Team Performance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Team Dynamics 2. Workload management 3. Occupational science 4. Training methods

Several labs and groups at JSC are pursuing different aspects of these technologies. The Quest Lab is performing research into the areas of networks and time delays. The Jupiter Facility is conducting research in many areas, including data storage capabilities and knowledge portal implementation. The Human Centered Autonomous and Assistant Systems Testbed (HCAAST) is conducting human centered design, development, and evaluation of intelligent autonomous and assistant systems of the type required for exploration missions. The HCAAST is also facilitating the connection of the Quest Lab, the Jupiter Facility, the Adjustable Autonomy Testbed, the BioPlex, and the ExPOC in order to conduct integrated tests and operational activities.

Automation is being considered as a key enabling technology to meet many of the aforementioned operational challenges. For example, exploration missions will require highly automated monitoring, planning, flight dynamics, and training systems. These systems will provide the capabilities for ground and onboard automated vehicle and crew health monitoring and control, automated and optimizing planning and scheduling, automated rendezvous, entry and landing systems, and in-situ, embedded, self-adapting training supported by simulation capabilities resident on board. These technologies will be developed, tested, and matured in current programs, to achieve increased operational efficiencies and improve safety. For future programs of exploration, this technology will be a requirement for achieving mission success.

Operations Assistants are being pursued as the key implementation of automation technology in the MCC. The remainder of this paper will focus on the development of Operations Assistants.

4. OPERATIONS ASSISTANTS – AUTOMATION

SOFTWARE WORKING AS PART OF THE TEAM

Operations Assistants are envisioned as intelligent software-based assistants for the flight controllers. They will essentially function as “backroom flight controllers” and work synergistically as part of the flight control team. They will be developed using state-of-the-art automation technology, including the use of intelligent agents. This will allow the Operations Assistants to be distributed and customizable as well as providing the capability to interface with mission data and existing flight controller software tools.

Functions of Operations Assistants

Operations Assistants will function as members of the flight control team and will perform the functions described in Table 2.

Table 2. Functions of Operations Assistants

FUNCTIONS OF OPERATIONS ASSISTANTS	
Assist flight controllers in maintaining mission cognizance	
Assist flight controllers in performing the following typical duties:	
a.	Data analysis
b.	Failure identification
c.	Off-nominal situation response
d.	Planning
e.	System and process management

By developing Operations Assistants for current missions, NASA will ensure that the technology is matured for future programs.

Unique Challenges in Implementing Operations Assistants

Although successfully implemented in a variety of unmanned areas such as satellites and robots, automation technology cannot be transferred directly to the MCC due to the unique challenges of manned space flight. These challenges are described in Table 3. Therefore, a team of experts from across NASA and academia is working to apply and extend state-of-the-art automation technology to manned space operations.

Table 3. Unique Challenges in Implementing Intelligent Agents in Manned Space Operations

CHALLENGE	BRIEF DESCRIPTION
Safety	Safety is of utmost concern because lives and national assets are at stake. Formal software development methods and stringent certification processes are essential to ensuring safety.
Teamwork	Operations Assistants must interact with the Flight Controllers in such a way as to function as part of the flight control team. They will essentially be software-based “back room flight controllers”
Reliability	Flight Controllers must be able to trust the software (i.e. understand how it works and trust that it will make the right decisions every time). The software must be certified for use in the Mission Control Center
Ease of Development and Maintenance	Flight Controllers must be able to easily update and modify the software when vehicle hardware or operations concepts (flight rules, procedures, etc.) change. Flight Controllers must be able to customize the software for their specific disciplines.
Challenges of Future Programs	Exploration missions will have added challenges due to the long distances and long durations. Many current MCC functions will move onboard the vehicle.

Technologies associated with Operations Assistants

The effective implementation of Operations Assistants will require technology advances and innovative solutions within the technical areas listed in Table 4.

Table 4. Technical Areas for Operations Assistant Development

TECHNICAL AREAS
1. Operations Assistant Architecture
2. Intelligent Agents
3. Knowledge Capture
4. Human Interfaces

The following paragraphs provide details of advances that will be required within each of these technical areas.

Operations Assistant Architecture—Existing architectures must be compared and synthesized into an architecture that functions in the ISS MCC and is extendable to onboard Operations Assistants. Its implementation will define the interface requirements and agent coordination standards used by the various analysis and data management agents, an integrated user interface, and selected existing MCC software.

This system “backbone” architecture infrastructure will be based on distributed software agents. It will provide a

common, open protocol for communication between agents, databases, and displays, to allow both custom agents and currently existing software systems to be integrated cleanly and transparently in a distributed manner. Representative prototype agents will be integrated into the architecture infrastructure. The agents will provide and read data using this protocol, link to telemetry, and interact with selected existing viewers, planning systems, and PC tools.

Intelligent Agents—Representative types of agents must be developed in order to enable widespread implementation of Operations Assistants throughout the ISS MCC.

These agents will function within the system architecture and interact with the integrated user interface. Agent development tools will allow users to update and customize the agents. The agents will utilize a variety of applicable technologies (model-based and case-based reasoning, petri nets, etc.). Agents will perform various duties including the following:

- Data, events, and process monitoring and analysis; anomaly detection and identification.
- Mission planning and anomaly response recommendations.
- Assistance with mission cognizance and ensuring mission objectives are met; procedure monitoring.
- Mission event logging and handover assistance.
- Data analysis and search capability to retrieve, analyze, and organize relevant procedures, reference material, log entries, and data for specific uses such as activity preparation and anomaly response.

Knowledge Capture—It will be necessary to address the emerging field of modeling tools for knowledge acquisition representation and also for system design, testing, and validation. It will be essential to develop modeling and specification tools and representations that support development, update, and certification of Operations Assistants by flight controllers with minimum burden on their time. Knowledge to be captured includes log events and log organization; flight rules; procedures; system goals and constraints; configurations and performance of systems and resources; and information to retrieve, collect and organize.

Human Interfaces—An integrated user interface will allow the flight controllers to interact effectively with the Operations Assistant. This includes accomplishing all of the functions listed earlier. State-of-the-art HCI and HCC design and analysis techniques will be utilized in designing and implementing the integrated user interface.

It is expected that the human interface will include the following:

- Advanced visual graphical interfaces for presentation and interaction with data, information, and agents.
- A natural language interface with speech understanding for interacting with Operations Assistant components such as a procedure assistant module. For example, natural language could be used for commanding, querying, and delegating operations.
- Immersive and non-immersive virtual reality interfaces. This may include a tele-presence aspect.
- Tools to allow users to update and customize the integrated user interface.

5. OPERATIONS ASSISTANTS – INITIAL PHASE:

LOGGING TOOL

One of the activities that flight controllers perform while in the MCC is to maintain a console log. This log contains entries with information about events, activities, and decisions that occurred during the flight controller's shift. They are essentially console notes. Most flight controllers keep these log entries in a text file. If, however, the log entries are stored in a data base, they can be accessed easier, can be viewed from remote locations (office, etc.), can be searched effectively, can be linked to other reference material, and can ultimately have automated entries inserted into the log. As these capabilities are incorporated, they will facilitate shifts in the operations paradigm such as a move to a more distributed operations environment and the use of more automation in the form of assistant software.

The initial phase of the operations assistant project consists of a prototype electronic logging application that utilizes a data base and a semi-automated handover report generation process. This lays the foundation for extensive future capabilities such as the use of advanced data base features (intelligent searches, tracking of open issues, reference material links) and links to information resources that will be utilized to provide an intelligent briefing assistant capability. In addition, the stage is set for connections to vehicle data, existing MCC software tools, and intelligent agents, which are essential for many of the Operations Assistant functions.

The work on the initial phase of the Operations Assistant is being accomplished by a team from NASA/JSC, NASA/Ames Research Center, and Ohio State University.

Development process and technical details

Human Centered Computing (HCC) experts from Ames Research Center and Ohio State University's Cognitive Systems Research Lab observed and interviewed multiple flight control positions. Two positions, the Station Duty Officer (SDO) and the Capsule Communicator (CAPCOM) positions were chosen for the initial phase. A specifications

document was written for the phased development of both the SDO [2] and CAPCOM [3] logging and handover application. Prototype versions of an SDO and CAPCOM logging and handover application has been developed and are undergoing user evaluation and testing.

The logging and handover applications use a Sybase data base with a Cold Fusion interface. The interactive editing of data base fields uses Java in order to provide custom features for various flight control positions. The Java applets are designed so that they can be easily customized for different flight control positions.

SDO Logging and Handover Application

The Station Duty Officer (SDO) Logging and Handover Application consists of a main logging page (figure 5) and a semi-automated handover report generation capability (figure 6).

Figure 5 – SDO Main Logging Screen

Figure 6 – Handover Report Development Screen

The main logging page consists of three primary sections. The lower section contains a new log entry field. The upper section provides a log viewing area. The navigation buttons are located across the top and right hand side.

CAPCOM Logging and Handover Application

The initial phase of CAPCOM Logging and Handover Application consists of a main logging page (figure 7) with an associated handover notes capability (not pictured).

The main logging page for the CAPCOM contains the same three primary sections. The lower section contains a new log entry field. The upper section provides a log viewing area. The navigation buttons are located across the top and right hand side.

Figure 7 – CAPCOM Main Logging Screen

Future Capabilities

The facets of development will include incorporation of a basic search feature and an open issues (also known as hot topics) generation and tracking capability.

While a basic application, the initial phase enables extensive future functionality as additional capabilities are incorporated (Table 5).

Table 5. Foundation for Future Capabilities

CAPABILITY	ENABLES THIS FUNCTION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advanced data base features 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intelligent searches Tracking of open issues Reference material links
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connections to mission data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automated logging Interface with data monitoring software agents Interface with failure identification agents
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connections to reference information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrated interface to flight rules, procedures, etc. Automated presentations to flight controllers for routine operations and failure response

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connections to existing MCC software tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interaction with legacy capabilities without redesign
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connections to intelligent agents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate capabilities of intelligent agents to achieve additional Operations Assistant capabilities

6. OPERATIONS ASSISTANTS – INITIAL PHASE:

FORMAL SPECIFICATION METHODS

It is expected that formal analysis methodologies will be an integral part of the development of the future capabilities of the Operations Assistant. While a limited amount of work has been done in this area to date, much remains.

The HCC analysis of the SDO and CAPCOM positions represents the initial use of scientific methodologies in approaching the Operations Assistant project.

The SDO and the electrical power system flight control positions have undergone a basic analysis using Petri Nets and Data Flow Diagrams. It is expected that the use of these or similar formal methods will provide a basis for determining which portions of a flight controller's task to automate and will define the interfaces and interactions between flight controller activities. This work was performed by La Salle University personnel working at JSC.

Data Flow Diagrams

Data Flow Diagrams are used to represent information flow, system boundaries, and environmental interactions. It is a popular structured analysis technique used during the analysis phase of system development to enhance communication with non-technical users. Data Flow Diagrams are used as a specification for developing the Petri Nets.

Petri Nets

Petri Nets are used to model the flow of control logic and sequencing at a level required for software design and development. They provide technical designers with a formal basis to rigorously investigate semantic properties of the system.

The Appendix contains an SDO Data Flow Diagram (Figure 8) and an SDO Petri Net (Figure 9) to provide an example of the level of specification that is contained in Data Flow Diagrams and Petri Nets. A detailed discussion of the mechanics of these formal specification methods and their application to the SDO may be found in [4].

7. OPERATIONS ASSISTANTS - THE NEXT PHASE

The next phase of the Operations Assistant project will systematically develop the four technical areas of architecture, intelligent agents, knowledge capture, and advanced human interfaces (refer to Section 4). The Operations Assistant project is addressing these technical challenges through collaborative work with experts in the field. Joint projects and collaborations with other NASA, military, academic, and commercial organizations are being actively pursued in order to achieve these goals.

Table 6 lists the milestones for a three stage approach. This approach is intended to provide the minimum amount of implementation necessary to successfully demonstrate the strategy for the application of Operations Assistant technologies within MOD.

Table 6. Stages of the Next Phase in Operations Assistant Development

STAGE	MILESTONES
Stage 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate advanced data base features into the logging and handover tool • Identify and begin implementation of two intelligent agents and the required architecture utilizing organizational lab resources. • Identify advanced user interface technologies to investigate in Stage 2 • Write interim white paper summarizing the research to date
Stage 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate two intelligent agents and the associated architecture utilizing organizational lab resources. • Identify the knowledge capture needs associated with the two intelligent agents • Implement the Advanced User Interface technologies identified in Stage 1 • Write a second interim white paper summarizing the research to date
Stage 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refine the two intelligent agents and the associated architecture • Develop the knowledge capture instrument for one of the intelligent agents • Refine the advanced user interfaces developed in Stage 2 • Compose white paper summarizing research to date and providing recommendations for the use of intelligent agents in mission operations in the future

Collaboration with other JSC Labs

The Operations Assistant project will be working closely with several of the labs mentioned in Section 3, especially

the Human Centered Autonomous and Assistant Systems Testbed (HCAAST). As mentioned earlier, the HCAAST is conducting human centered design, development, and evaluation of intelligent autonomous and assistant systems with an emphasis on the type of system required for exploration missions. Although the emphasis is on exploration missions, much of the HCAAST work is relevant to current ISS operations. It is expected that the two projects will leverage their activities. For example, the HCAAST is already utilizing the logging and handover report application to log environmental data received from the Adjustable Autonomy Testbed and utilize it with an Intelligent Briefing Assistant. The HCAAST project has modified the application to run with an Oracle data base and is making additional modifications that may feed back into the Operations Assistant project.

Additionally, the HCAAST and its associated network of labs and facilities will provide an environment in which to develop and test prototypes of advanced software capabilities such as intelligent agents and intelligent briefing assistants prior to their insertion into space station mission operations.

Collaboration with Flight Controllers

The Operations Assistant project is working closely with selected flight control positions. Many of the flight control positions currently utilize software programs that provide specific functions. In many cases the outputs of one program are utilized as inputs in another process. There is interest in automating the data transfers between selected programs. The implementation of this type of automated data transfer between existing MCC software programs will be the first step in the development of an architecture that will support increasingly sophisticated data transfer processes between software modules and agents.

Collaboration with Other Organizations

The Operations Assistant project will continue to collaborate with other NASA centers and academia. As noted earlier, it will take the collaboration of multiple NASA organizations as well as experts from academia and other interested organizations to effectively solve the complex technical challenges associated with implementing intelligent agents in the manned flight operations.

8. SUMMARY

MOD is facing many unique operational challenges in the years ahead. Many technologies, as outlined in sections 3 and 4, will have to be advanced and implemented in existing operations in order to enhance execution of complex international space station operations as well as exploration operations. Automation technology, in the form of Operations Assistants, is being pursued as a solution to many of the operations challenges. The Logging and Handover Application is the first step toward the

implementation of Operations Assistants in the MCC. The next phase will advance the use of Operations Assistants by focusing on the technical areas of architecture, agents, knowledge capture tools, and advanced user interfaces.

The continued collaboration of multiple NASA centers and academia, as well as the participation of other interested organizations, will be necessary in order to solve the many unique technical challenges associated with the effective implementation of Operations Assistants in manned space operations.

ACRONYMS

CAPCOM	Capsule Communicator
ExPOC	Exploration Planning and Operations Center
HCC	Human Centered Computing
HCI	Human Computer Interface
ISS	International Space Station
JSC	Johnson Space Center
MCC	Mission Control Center
MOD	Mission Operations Directorate
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
SDO	Station Duty Officer

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The following people contributed to the work included in this paper:

- Greg Alexander, JSC, Titan LinCom Corporation
- Klaus Christoffersen, Ohio State University
- Renee Chow, Ohio State University
- Dan Dexter, JSC, Titan LinCom Corporation
- Jane T. Malin, JSC
- John O'Neill, Ames Research Center, RIACS
- Charles A. Shultz, JSC, United Space Alliance
- Madjid Tavana, La Salle University
- Carroll G. Thronesberry, JSC, Metrica Inc.
- Roxana Wales, Ames Research Center, Caelum Research Corporation

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APPENDIX

Figure 8 – SDO Data Flow Diagram

Figure 9 – SDO Petri Net